

STIGMATIZATION AND CHALLENGES OF REINTEGRATION OF WOMEN WITH VVF/RVF IN AKWA IBOM STATE, NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

This study examined stigmatization and challenges of reintegration of women with Vesico-vaginal fistula (VVF) in Akwa Ibom State. The research design adopted for this study was phenomenology. Data were collected from a sample of seventeen women using interview. Data collected for the study were analyzed manually using the inductive approach of analyzing qualitative data. The findings of the study indicated that women living with VVF in Akwa Ibom State are stigmatized. The stigmatization ranges from isolation, abandonment, mockery and insult. The stigmatization makes life difficult for them since most of them lack or receive very little economic support from their mates and families. After successful repair, the Family Life Centre at Mbribit Itam adopted various methods of reintegration of these women. The most common reintegration strategy was learning of skills and counselling. The study also identified family support as one of the available reintegration strategies used by many. It was concluded that women suffering from VVF are stigmatized and that the common reintegration strategies adopted after their repairs were skill training, counselling and family support. It was recommended that reintegration program designers should bear in mind that all girls and women with fistula are not the same, as such, reintegration strategies need to address the different situations in which these women may find themselves.

KEYWORDS: Stigmatization, reintegration, women and vesico-vaginal fistula

INTRODUCTION

Vesico-vaginal fistula (VVF) is considered as the abnormal connection between the urinary tract and the vagina such that there is an incessant, uncontrollable leakage of urine into the vaginal tract. According to Villey (2016), VVF is an abnormal communication between the urinary bladder and the vagina that results in the continuous involuntary discharge of urine into the vaginal vault; the pathogenesis of VVF is expressed by the contraction of the pelvis, the prolonged and obstructed labour (labour usually becomes obstructed, when the pelvis is too

small for the passage of the baby) resulting in ischemia of tissues between the bladder and vagina (Akpe, 2013). Few weeks later; the woman experiences sloughing of the tissues and fistula occurs, this could lead to diverse complications like vaginal or urinary tract infections, hygiene problems, stool or gas that leaks through the vagina, irritated or inflamed skin around the vagina, an abscess (a swollen clump of infected tissue with pus that could be life-threatening), and also the risk of fistula forming again. The hallmark symptom of VVF is the uncontrolled leakage of urine into the vagina (Akpeji, 2012).

Though vesicovaginal fistula is a global problem, the health problem appears to be particularly common in Africa. Despite international and national efforts toward the prevention and treatment of obstetric fistula (OF) among women, the problem still remains a major concern and a serious challenge in low income countries where access to emergency obstetric care and skilled birth attendant are insufficient (Delamou *et al.*, 2016).

Over the years, studies have been carried out on cases of obstetric fistula based on hospital records in Nigeria. The National Foundation on Vesico-Vaginal Fistulae (2013) noted that the actual incidence of fistula is not easy to calculate. Harrison (2014) suggested that the incidence might be closer to 80 per 100,000. In Nigeria, the number of cases of VVF and the frequency of occurrence is unknown. This is as a result of the absence of large-scale community based studies.

According to the Federal Ministry of Health in Agu (2013), between 500,000 and 1,000,000 women/girls are living with VVF, and an estimate of up to 80,000 new cases annually. The incidence is estimated at two per 1,000 deliveries. These estimates are based on information gathered from victims who attend established medical facilities seeking healthcare. The reality is, however, that most sufferers, due to either distance or cost, never make it to any formal medical establishment for appropriate attention. There are various predisposing factors to VVF, some of which are; marital status, age, level of education among others.

Researchers have identified marital status as a significant predictor of the likelihood of developing obstetric fistula (Andargie and Debu, 2017; Barageine *et al.*, 2014; Otoo-Oyortey *et al.*, 2014). In a recent study to examine factors associated with the prevalence of obstetric fistula in Ethiopia, Andargie and Debu (2017) found that women whose first marriage fell between the ages of 15 and 19 years old were 87.4% less likely to develop obstetric fistula than those whose first marriage was at an age ranging below 15 years of age. In the same study the researchers indicated that women who first married at age ranging between 20 to 24 years old were 81% less likely to experience obstetric fistula than those who were married before the age of 15 when controlling for other variables in the logistic model. Also, in their study aimed at examining the risk factors for obstetric fistula in West Uganda, Barageine *et al.*, (2014) indicated a significant association between being single and developing obstetric fistula compared to being married. In a qualitative study using 20 women who had previously had repair of obstetric fistula in Malawi, Drew *et al.* (2016) found 80% of the study population to be married prior to the development of the fistula.

Similarly, a literature review of both quantitative and qualitative data from relevant obstetrics and gynecology websites and journals to gather evidence on causes and consequences of obstetric fistula in Ethiopia, by Tollosa and Kibret (2013) revealed a statistically significant association between marital status and experience of obstetric fistula

(p -value < 0.001). In another study, Lufumpa *et al.*, (2018) found that cultural practices around marriage played a key role in the perpetuation of obstetric fistulas sub-Saharan Africa. The researchers also found that dowries decreased with age of the bride in some cultures which served as an incentive for parents to give their daughters in marriage at a younger age. Furthermore, Delamou *et al.* (2016) examined the estimated proportions of failure of fistula closure and incontinence among women undergoing obstetric fistula repair in Guinea. The researchers found that majority of the obstetric fistula patients were married ($n = 523, 69.4\%$).

In addition, Basheer and Pumpaibool (2015) revealed age at first marriage as a significant factor in the occurrence of obstetric fistula in Kebbi State, Nigeria. In their study of fistula and socio-demographic characteristics, Basheer and Pumpaibool (2015) found age at first marriage to be a significant factor in the occurrence of vesico vaginal fistula. Almost all of the women with vesico vaginal fistula got married within the age range between 12 and 15 years old in Kebbi state, Nigeria. The importance of child marriage in this case is the fact that a girl is more likely to get pregnant and deliver a baby that she is not physically and psychological prepared for, when that girl is married at a very young age (Pandya and Bhanderi, 2015). Even more important, Pandya and Bhanderi (2015) found that there is an increased rate of maternal morbidity and mortality in such young mothers.

The psychological consequences of obstetric fistula are substantial, with depression and early death from suicide (FIGO, 2016). Holtz and Ahmed (2017) demonstrate that women suffering the ordeal of fistula are abandoned by their husbands and family, and are shunned from their communities. Fistula is considered a “social calamity” and women with fistula are often ostracized by their husbands, families, and communities. The condition is often considered a sexually transmitted disease and viewed as a punishment from God. Most women with fistulas report disturbed socio-psychosexual lives and are usually deserted by their husbands. Often, until they are cured, married women with obstetric fistula are sent back to their parents' home where they are not allowed to cook food, participate in social events, or to perform religious rituals. Not only that mourning a dead child is almost inevitable for a woman with a fistula from obstructed labour, but she soon finds herself fighting for her own survival, social position, and value in society. Mentally she is tormented and devastated.

Physical/ medical consequences of obstetric fistula include ulceration, infection, foot drop, kidney diseases and dehydration. In almost all cases of obstetric fistula the leaking of urine and the offensive smell makes the women highly stigmatized and ashamed of themselves (Holtz and Ahmed, 2017; Cook *et al.*, 2014). Consequently, eating, sleeping and praying alone (social isolation), abandonment and divorce, loss of self-esteem and economic deprivation occur. Due to misperceptions surrounding the condition, many of the women survivors see themselves as wretched or cursed, isolating them from their communities and preventing them from seeking help and treatment.

According to the needs assessment carried out by MOH and UNFPA (2014) stigma is an elusive concept, but one that is increasingly recognized as a major component in the perception of the ill person. In Mwingi, Kwale and Homa Bay districts the issue of stigma is not so explicit. The general feeling was that their immediate families did not reject women with fistulas. However, the women, out of their own volition segregated themselves from others because of the embarrassment occasioned by the foul smell. However, having a fistula among the Pokot attracts a social stigma from the community in that the women cannot stay

with others or even cook for the family. Worse still is the situation where a husband returns the wife to her father and demands a refund of the bride price especially if the fistula occurs at birth of the first child.

Fistula is invariably devastating to the lives of women who survive and endure it (Cook et al., 2014). Affected women are frequently driven from their marriages, families and communities to a point of becoming socially invisible and forgotten. They experience a foul smell that results from leaking urine and faecal incontinence and are barred from family activities like cooking and at times driven into isolation. Denied family support, the malnutrition and poverty is aggravated and at times when they can, such women have depended on begging, prostitution or stigmatizing employment. Arguably, social stigma contributes further to women's poverty and gender inequalities.

Women living with fistula experience seclusion and stigma owing to the offensive smell and cultural taboos and this may still be a challenge even after corrective surgery. These women may also face problem reintegrating into their local communities that may desert them or regard them as unclean or cursed. In many cases the situation is aggravated by the increasing poverty women with fistula face due to their limited income generating resources (WHO, 2019).

Obstetric fistula is an international public health problem with serious psychosocial consequences. It is characterized by significant emotional disturbance due to continuous involuntary leakage of urine and/or faeces and the resultant discrimination as a result of persistent offensive odour. It is prevalent in resources-poor countries of the world of which Nigeria is included. The experience has overturned the life of many women and makes it miserable. Many have lived for many years rejected and abandoned without hope to live a normal life again. Others have contemplated suicide because of their situations, but thanks to the management of the Family Life Centre at Mbribit Itam and other centres in Nigeria that have given hope to these women through successful surgical repair.

Over the years, there has been a great achievement in the physical treatment of many obstetric fistula patients. However, the long term emotional, psychological, social and economic needs of women after surgical repair have received little attention. For instance, Nduka *et al.* (2023) reported that psycho-social support for women living with obstetric fistula in Nigeria is limited. Nduka further reported that women living with obstetric fistula in Nigeria were found to be ostracized, abandoned by families and friends, stigmatized and discriminated against, which led to depression, loneliness, loss of self-esteem, self-worth and identity. These women also face the problem of reintegrating into their local communities that may desert them or regard them as unclean or cursed. Degge *et al.* (2019) reported a rehabilitation program for rehabilitation offered to the women who were affected by obstetric fistula, which made them hopeful and resilient. However, there is paucity of research on the reintegration of women suffering from obstetric fistula in Akwa Ibom State. To bridge this gap, the present study examined stigmatization and reintegration challenges of women with obstetric fistula in Akwa Ibom State, with specific focus on availability of re-integration programs and coping strategies.

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

The Concept of Vesico-Vaginal Fistula (VVF)

Vesico-vaginal fistula an abnormal opening between the vagina, bladder and/or rectum, often caused by prolonged obstructed labour and is marked by incontinence of urine, faeces or both (El-Azab *et al.*, 2019). It is closely and directly linked to maternal mortality and morbidity. Basically, there are two main types: (a) Vesico-vaginal fistula (VVF) which is a situation in which the abnormal opening is between the bladder and the vagina resulting in continuous leakage of urine and, (b) Recto-vaginal fistula (RVF), which is a situation when the opening is between the rectum and the vagina resulting in leakage of faeces.

The earliest and oldest evidence of obstructed labour was discovered in the remains of Queen Henhenit, who was a wife of King Mentuhotep II of Egypt sometime in 2050 BC. This observation was made when the Queen's mummy, on discovery by Edouard Naville, was sent to the Metropolitan Museum of Art, New York in 1907. A thorough observation of the Queen's mummy indicated that the vagina was normal while there was a mass of tissue 10 cm long, possibly intestine sticking out through the anus.

In 1923, the mummy was returned to Cairo for detailed clinical examination by Professor D. E Derry, which showed that there was a tear in the bladder connecting to the vagina. A closer examination also indicated that the pelvic bone was abnormal in shape, approximating that of apes. Considering the width of the pelvis, the examiner believed it was too small or narrow to allow a passage of fetal head, and that the severe pain and damage done to the bladder and vagina could have been responsible for the death of Queen Henhenit (Zacharin in Agu, 2013).

Prior to the above discovery, an Arabo-Persian physician, named Avicenna, who died in 1037 AD, was the first individual to observe that urinary incontinence in women may be as a result of fistula consequent upon obstructed labour (Agu, 2013). While linking difficult labour to fistula, he advised on pregnancy prevention, especially among young girls, he thus said “in cases in which women are married young, and in patients who have weak bladders, the physician should instruct the patient in the ways of prevention of pregnancy. In these patients, bulk of foetus may cause a tear in the bladder which results in incontinence of urine. The condition is incurable and remains so till death.”

The end of 1600 BC however, became a remarkable period because that was when several clearer descriptions of fistula started coming up. In 1597, Felix Platter, Basle gave the following description of fistula: “as a consequence of a first labour, the young country girl had the opening of the bladder rent to such a degree that there was a long gapping furrow in its place, and the open bladder could be seen on account of this injury, there is a constant involuntary discharge of urine, and the surrounding parts become excoriated and inflamed” (Zacharin in Agu, 2013).

At the beginning of 19th century, major progress was made in the repair and treatment of Vesico-vaginal fistula. Notable among the physicians at the time were de Lmballe, Wutser, Simon, Sims, Emmet and Bozeman (Agu, 2013). Between 1845 and 1859, Doctor Marion Sims has become famous for his aggressive discoveries of instruments and materials used in closing enormous fistula. Till date Sim has been praised for recognizing that health problem faced by women required urgent medical and surgical attention (Fasakin, 2007).

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Several studies report gathered from hospitals in Nigeria show that less than one percent of hospital deliveries are complicated by fistula Harrison (2014). Monitoring of 22,774 deliveries in Zaria from 1976 to 1979 found out those 79 women who had developed VVF was as a result of obstructed labour primarily due to cephalopelvic disproportion. Ijaiya et al (2010). In a report titled; Vesico Vaginal Fistula: A Review of Nigerian Experience, revealed that many Nigerian women are living with vesico-vaginal fistula with the annual obstetric fistula incidence estimated at 2.11 per 1000 births with its prevalent more in northern Nigeria than in southern Nigeria. Obstetric fistula accounts for 84.1%– 100% of the vesicovaginal fistula and prolonged obstructed labour is consistently the most common cause (65.9%–96.5%) in all the series.

Other common causes include caesarean section, advanced cervical cancer, uterine rupture, and Gishiricut. The identified predisposing factors were early marriage and pregnancy, which were rampant in northern Nigeria, while unskilled birth attendance and late presentation to the health facilities was common nationwide. Among the significant contributory factors to high rate of unskilled birth attendance were poverty, illiteracy, ignorance, restriction of women's movement, non-permission from husband, and transportation. All but one Nigerian studies revealed that primiparous women were the most vulnerable group. Pregnancy outcome was dismal in most cases related to delivery with still birth rate of 87%– 91.7%. Stigmatization, divorce and social exclusion were common complications. Overall fistula repair success rate was between 75% and 92% in a few centres that offer such services, Ijaiya *et al* (2010).

Lister in Agu (2013) four years study on 320 cases of obstructed labour in the University College Hospital Ibadan (UCH), observed that (6.6%) 21 of the obstructed labour resulted in VVF. Of the 21 cases, 2 healed spontaneously, 10 were repaired, 1 patient died before repair was possible and nine patients remained untraced. In the same study, he observed 17,230 delivery cases, giving an incidence of obstructed labour of 1 in 189 deliveries accounting for (27.2%) 44 of the 162 maternal deaths in the period.

According to Thaddeus and Maine in Odu and Cleland (2013) analyzed the contributory factors to the delayed treatment in the developing countries. Factors were grouped into three broad categories which were termed the three phases of delay; firstly, delay is looked on the part of the pregnant women, her family or both; secondly, delay in getting to a well-established health care facility and lastly, delay in promptly receiving health care once

their destination has been reached. These delays from available literature are due to the means of getting to the exact place where adequate health-care facility can be sought. Most of the VVF patients come from very poor background, and as such cannot readily get money to transport themselves to the city's health centres. It is when the health of a VVF patient is being seriously threatened and affected that the husband or relatives gather their few belongings for sale in order to get transportation fare to and fro a health centre in the city. The last delay is very peculiar to the Nigeria health system. Some of the health personnel are always very careless with the lives of others, and some get discouraged and prefer to stay at home to be attended to by the traditional birth attendants who are always very caring about the lives of others though they may not have the required knowledge education to carry out what is required of them. Apart from the carelessness of the personnel, there are shortages of supplies and equipment and the interminable internal delays involved in making a marginal work. (Wall in Odu and Cleland, 2013).

Challenges of Women Living with VVF

Evidence shows that many women and girls with obstetric fistulas faced many psychological problems such as humiliation (reported by 97.2% of victims); abandonment, stigmatization, and loneliness (reported by 95.8%) (Ezekiel *et al.*, 2021; Oluwasola and Bello, 2020). Similar studies showed that 85% of women experienced separation from their husbands, and 95.4% reported despair (Baba, 2014; Ezekiel *et al.*, 2021). Women with obstetric fistulas are often afraid and uncertain about their future with sexual partners, marriage, sex, pregnancy, childbirth, and reintegration into the neighborhood community (Letchworth *et al.*, 2018; Khisa *et al.*, 2017). Similarly, other evidence in the developing world shows a divorce rate of 36% to 67%, a stillborn rate of 55.6% to 85%, childlessness of 83.3%, frequent maternal loss of self-esteem, depression, and suicidal thoughts. Urinary inconsistency due to obstetric fistula affects patient self-esteem and quality of life. These can lead to secondary morbidity, disability, infertility, and significant costs for women with obstetric fistula (Ruiz and Kaiser, 2017). However, due to more than one factor, women with fistulas nevertheless live in silence with suffering, and repairing their emotional harm has not gotten much emphasis so far (Bakundane, 2016).

Psychological Consequences of VVF

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Stigmatization of Women Living with VVF

According to the needs assessment carried out by MOH and UNFPA (2014) stigma is an elusive concept, but one that is increasingly recognized as a major component in the perception of the ill person. In Mwingi, Kwale and Homa Bay districts the issue of stigma is not so explicit. The general feeling was that their immediate families did not reject women with fistulas. However, the women, out of their own volition segregated themselves from others because of the embarrassment occasioned by the foul smell. However, having a fistula among the Pokot attracts a social stigma from the community in that the women cannot stay with others or even cook for the family. Worse still is the situation where a husband returns the wife to her father and demands a refund of the bride price especially if the fistula occurs at birth of the first child.

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Women living with fistula experience seclusion and stigma owing to the offensive smell and cultural taboos and this may still be a challenge even after corrective surgery. These women may also face problem reintegrating into their local communities that may desert them or regard them as unclean or cursed. In many cases the situation is aggravated by the increasing poverty women with fistula face due to their limited income generating resources (WHO, 2019).

Reintegration Strategies of Women Living with VVF

Reintegration refers to the re-acceptance of the obstetric fistula patients back into their social environment following their harrowing experiences of either fecal or urinary incontinence and in some instances, both of which have been associated with loss of self-esteem and dignity. It is therefore aimed at enabling them realize their full potential in life and gain emotional and psychosocial stability through culturally accepted counselling, peer and community support (Khisra, 2010). Rehabilitation on the other hand, refers to any experience that strives to improve the quality of lives of women before or after corrective surgery

(Lombard, 2010). It is sometimes used interchangeably with reintegration, and includes programs aimed to improve overall status of women, through empowerment and enhancement of their socio-economic status such as vocational

Nigeria having 40% of the global burden of obstetric fistula has put in place measures to eradicate obstetric fistula and its sequels (Ojengbede, 2017). The federal ministry of health designed a National Strategic Framework for Elimination of Obstetric Fistula in Nigeria which guides activities conducted at Federal, state, local level, civil society, and those of and by development partners. The country has 12 dedicated centers for obstetric fistula surgery which also take care of reintegration and rehabilitation as important components of holistic care. Each year, the centers repair 2000 to 4000 obstetric fistula patients, however, the backlog is enormous and it requires more than 100 years to deal with it while ignoring new cases who are 20,000 per annum. The Federal Ministry of Health and stakeholders are dedicated to reduce obstetric fistula incidence rate by 50% and increase rehabilitation by the same percentage.

A study done in Nigeria by Capes et al. (2011) on postoperative care pointed out that all fistula centers and some teaching hospitals have rehabilitation centers where patients can be referred to after repair. In addition to government activities, the Foundation for Women's Health Research and Development (FORWARD) and AMREF for Health provide a holistic approach of care through surgery, and supporting women to have positive rehabilitation experiences through skills training, and creating community awareness, health education, offering gifts in form of clothing and soap and home based care (Fistula Foundation, 2018). A study conducted by Ojengbede (2017) stated that 67% of women who have had successful repair need family support as a backup for their effective reintegration while 60% consider work resumption as imperative in making them feel normal and accepted. In Tanzania, same factors were mentioned by 68% of the successfully repaired obstetric fistula patients as imperative in their effective reintegration.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Goffman's Stigma Theory – Goffman (1963)

The study is guided by Erving Goffman's stigma theory (Goffman, 1963). Goffman defines stigma as an 'attribute that is deeply discrediting', reducing the person that possesses a particular quality 'from a whole and usual person to a tainted and discredited one' whereby consequently the person is socially discounted. For Goffman, the stigmatized can be either discreditable or discredited. The former refers to people that possess a stigmatizing characteristic but have not yet been discredited, mainly because this quality has not yet been fully revealed. The latter relates to those who have been socially judged and marginalized by their surrounding social world.

Stigmatization is the result of a socialization process whereby the person with the quality generally holds the same identity beliefs as normal (i.e. persons without a stigmatizing characteristic) and may in fact feel normal when alone. This is then displaced by a sense of deep abnormality in the presence of normal, frequently resulting in feelings of self-hate, self-isolation, depression and/or hostility. Goffman describes the socialization of the personal identity of a stigmatized person as a process of information control. The discreditable person manages information, continually judging whether or not to reveal their stigmatic quality.

When the person is actually discredited, they are faced with managing the tension that will ensue. Passing is a central concept developed by Goffman, which he uses to help describe information control. This refers to when a person with a stigmatic quality manages information so that they can partly or fully 'pass' as a normal. Given the rewards of being normal, the stigmatized will attempt to pass if they can. Passers draw on several information control strategies. These can include the concealment of stigmatic symbols or use of dis-identifiers.

The relationship of the stigmatized with normal highlights their deviation from societal norms. Consequently, the stigmatized manage their social deviance by creating their own social norms that they will measure themselves against, alienating themselves from the community that upholds the stigmatizing norms, or employing a variety of passing techniques to manage information and their status among the stigmatized and normal.

This theory is quite relevant to this study as it explains the effect of stigmatization on individuals. These ones' always live with the tension that comes from stigmatization and can hardly become emotionally stable. Such individuals can find it challenging to succeed economically as many who stigmatized that may not patronize them or discourage others from patronizing them. The theory further indicated that people can cope with stigmatization by managing information about their reason of stigmatization.

METHODOLOGY

The research design adopted for this study was descriptive phenomenology. According to Falaye (2018) phenomenological research is to understand the essence of a social phenomenon from the perspective of those who have experience it. This has two implications. One, people experience what is important for them to know and how they interpret what they experienced within their domain. The second implication is methodological. Phenomenological research design was considered appropriate for this study since the researcher was also interested in conducting in-depth interview to find out the challenges of women living with VVF and that of those who have undergone successful repair.

This study was conducted in the Family Life Centre Located in Mbribit Itam, Itu Local Government Area. The Family Life Centre is located at Mbribit Itam in Itu Local Government Area. It is *an efficient reproductive health and family Health counselling centre with highly skilled personnel*. Family Life Centre/ V.V.F Hospital is a Faith Based hospital which was established in the 1980s. The idea of Family Life Centre/V.V.F Hospital was the initiative of an MMM (Medical Missionaries of Mary sister) obstetrician/ gynecologist - Sr. Dr. Ann Ward. In 1960s while working in St. Luke's hospital, Anua, Sr. Dr. Ward was touched by the large number of young women whose lives were damaged by dehumanizing obstetric injuries. She started offering surgeries to these ladies at that time in St. Luke's Hospital, Anua. As the number increased, it became difficult for her to get enough bed space for them and she also realized they needed specialized care both before and after the surgery. It was then she conceived the idea to get a place for these women who would nurture a supportive environment and where she could train staff on the special kind of care these women needed. Hence Family Life Centre/V.V.F Hospital /VVF hospital was given birth to (<https://www.familylifelifehospital.org/details/Philosophy/1>).

The population of the study was made up of all women suffering from VVF who were receiving treatment at the Family Life Centre/VVF Hospital Mbricit Itam as at January 2022, the centre reported that 145 patients registered for the VVF/RVF operation. (The Guardian, 2022). A sample size of 17 women was selected for the study. The selection was done using convenience sampling technique. According to Fleetwood (2019) convenience sampling is defined as a method adopted by researchers where they collect research data from a conveniently available pool of respondents. The researcher used an instrument entitled “Challenges of VVF Interview Schedule” was used in collecting data for the study. Data collected for the study were analyzed manually using the inductive approach of analyzing qualitative data.

RESULT

Level of Stigmatization Experienced by Women Living with VVF

The women living with VVF are stigmatized and isolated by member of their families and the community. There is little interaction between a victim of VVF and her community. When there is any form of interaction, they are ridiculed and made to feel less of human being. Some of them are isolated to live in a separate house or room with little interaction with other members of the family and the community in general. Only those women who have the means to package themselves without the notice of others are free from ridicule in the community, but cannot escape from that of their immediate family members. Narrating this challenge, one fistula patient expresses her experience thus;

I lived with my brother and my uncle. I used to change cloths frequently and used rags to collect the urine feces that used to come out. I tried to keep myself very clean, but I always smell because of the leaking urine and feces. My uncle's wife used to cause me and I cried all day long. She could not bear me staying with them again, and my uncle had to send me away to stay in a building without good doors and window. Some people thought I was mad. I could not stay where others are. Even my friends would always disperse if I go to where they are gathering. It was one day, as my uncle's wife was causing me that a nurse that brought me here heard her and asked of where I am. She directed her to me and the nurse took me here for treatment. I really thank God that the surgery was successful.

Another survivor describes her experience while living with VVF this way;

Some looked down upon me. They looked down upon me and laughed at me. They said look at her, she is torn. She is torn at the buttocks! That time, I couldn't talk to people, because they would throe bad words at me. I always avoid where people gather and it was very difficult to even attend church because no one will sit close to me. This is because my seat will always be wet before the close of church for the day. It was very disturbing until I was treated. This is me now, I can stay close to people without smelling.

This was corroborated by key informants who reported that women living with VVF face social stigma and isolation. They are alienated from their husbands, their parents, the other family members and the community at large. In some cases, these women are sent to stay outside the compound so as not to bring shame to their families; they eat and live on their own. Secluded, they also face other challenges such as lack of food or even drinking water.

Challenges of Reintegration of VVF Survivors

The challenges women face after a successful VVF surgery was discussed with some of the women. They mention economic challenge and stigmatization as the main challenge they face. Some of the women mention that many people who knew about their situation find it difficult to believe that they are totally free. They further mentioned that many people still relate with them after the surgery the same way they did before the surgery. For instance, many people who knew about their situation before the surgery would change their sitting location if they happened to sit with them. One of the survivor commented;

I still find it difficult to make people believe me that I do not smell like before. I always feel ashamed when people change their seats when I happened to sit with them. Some of my friends do not still allow me to share in preparing food in some occasions. When I attended marriage and ladies were asked to come and share food, many people who knew about my situation refuse to collect food from me. I was very ashamed of myself when I noticed that they collected from others after rejecting mine.

Another respondent also mentioned stigmatization as a challenge to their reintegration after the surgery. She narrated her experience, thus;

I thank God almighty that I had finally have a cure to my illness. To God be the glory. Though I am free from my sickness, my mother in-law is the one that tries to annoy me. My husband do not have any problem with me, and I always thank God for him. My mother in-law is the problem I am having. She has not been eating my food since this sickness started and will be discussing me to others in the community. When I came back from the surgery, I told her that I am now free from the sickness, she has not still believe me. I noticed that she continue throwing my food away anytime I give her food, so I stopped. I still find it difficult to convince my mother in-law that I am free from the sickness.

Aside from stigmatization being a challenge to the reintegration of women who had successful VVF repair, means of survival is also a great challenge to many. Among these are those who do not have parents or were divorce by their husbands. Some of them are attaching themselves to some religious organizations in order to get support from there. Others are totally depending on the family life centre for their survival and help provided by visitors to the family life centre. This makes it difficult for some of them to mix freely with others since they are still having this feeling of being inferior to others. One of the respondents

commented;

Since I don't have what to do, I decided to stay here. At least, I am being provided with food here. If I go now, I will not have means to survive. I know how I suffered before getting to this place. It is only God that touches the heart of some people to give me food. I use to stay for some days without food. It is even better here, I am only praying that God should make a way for me to have what I can use to take care of myself.

Another respondent commented;

Life was hard when I was suffering from this sickness and it is still hard by now. I used to run a restaurant business. When I had this problem, I couldn't do it again. People did not like to come and eat in the place. My husband left me and survived all alone. I had to sell most of my belongings in order to survive. I have nothing left for me except my cloths. How to start the business again is my greatest challenge. I sometimes go to some church and tell people about my situation to see if I can get help. I am not a lazy person, and I don't want to beg. All what I need is the means to start my own business. Since I cannot achieve that, the only option for me is to continue staying here in the family life centre.

In addition to economic challenge, some of them equally reported having challenge with participation in social life. One of the women commented;

Taking part in social life is painful for us as we think of our odour always. For example, going to church, going to a marital ceremony, and coming to the house to stay and chat with neighbours is difficult. The difficulty was socializing as before. I'm still trying to see how I can mix with other people without feeling ashamed of myself.

Reintegrating VVF Survivors

Some of the women who have survived VVF repair mentioned some of the strategies that help or prevented their reintegration after the surgery. Some of these were supported by key informants who also mentioned other strategies that they have observed during their interaction with VVF survivors. These strategies that influence the reintegration of VVF survivors were discussed, followed by highlights findings on proposed avenues for reintegrating VVF survivors. Most of the proposed avenues were reported by both the survivors and key informants.

- ***Skill training***

Some of VVF survivors were trained by the management of the VVF centre at Mbribit Itam on various skills such as tailoring and hair dressing. Those who received these training reported occupying their minds with the training, instead of always thinking of their situation. Others mentioned that the training helped them to start mixing freely with people especially with the different trainers employed to teach them the skills and they also feel a bit free to interact with visitors who come to the facility. One of the survivor commented;

I really appreciate the management of family life centre for giving me the opportunity to learn tailoring after my successful surgery. Initially, I was thinking how people will look at me if I try getting close to them, but through this tailoring business, I am close to others who suffered the same situation as mine, I am equally close to my trainers who did not even suffer what I went through. I even have the opportunity to go out and buy clothing materials for the training and people do not know what I went through because I do not smell like before. I am really happy that many people that I meet out there do not despise me like before. I feel more comfortable interacting with other people gradually. My only fear now is about those that knew about my situation before now, but I believe they will notice that I no longer smell like before.

Also, another survivor who learned hair dressing has this to say;

I really thank God for the opportunity to come here and be healed. My condition was terrible. My mother died and my father married another woman, the woman used to maltreat us and will not give us food, and that was why I had a boyfriend that put me into this trouble and everybody including my boyfriend abandoned me. I used to cry every day. Thank God that I am healed and I also learn this hair dressing that can help me to make my money and survive. This hair dressing business will help me not to go back and depend on my father and my step mother. I don't feel ashamed staying with people again.

Aside from learning skills as a means of rehabilitating these women, there was also provision for counselling. Many of the survivors have taken advantage of the various counselling session to adjust their mind and belief that they are still humans and have self-worth. They believe that they can still be loved by others and can still live a normal life despite what happened to them. These ones still hope that they would marry one day, but that they would do all what it takes to prevent this situation from repeating itself. One of the respondent commented;

First of all, I want to thank God almighty for what he has done in my life in this Family Life Centre. I did not believe I will ever mix with people again. My mother has tried many places, but there was no cure to my situation until we were directed to this place after many years of suffering. Initially, when I had this problem, I really hate men. I did not think I will marry again, but through the counselling that we used to have here, I learned that I can still marry and that it is possible for me to still have children. If a man comes now, I will still get married.

Some of the survivor also mentioned family support as one of the important factors that helped them in the reintegration process. In cases where the family supported the survivors, they settled down better and were able to live normal lives, get children and do business. One survivor who had been received support from her husband commented;

My husband has really tried for me. When I was suffering from the sickness, he did not abandon me. He did all he could to help me in my situation. Even though her relatives advised him to send me away and marry another woman, he refused. He said I did not have this problem in my father's house. Now that I have been successfully repaired, he has not abandoned me. He still provides me with food here and I do visit him from time to time. I only stay here to learn this tailoring. When am done, I will go back to my husband. He is a good man, God will bless him.

Other who have been taken back by their parents and cared for has also reported feeling relieved and being able to associate with people. One of the survivor who reported being abandoned by his father and step mother while she was suffering from the sickness reported that after treatment, her father came to take her home. She was advised not to return home without a skill in order not to be a burden to her parents again. In words, she stated;

Life was not fair to me. When I had this problem, I was abandoned by my stepmother and father. Now that I have been repaired, I was very happy to see my father coming to take me home. Initially, I was thinking where I will go to, and how my parents will look at me. Now he is the one that asked me to come back home, I am very happy about that.

However, not every woman who had undergone repair was able to get back and receive support from families. Some who had been chased away from home are yet to see any of their family members visiting them. They reported experiencing a lot of problems due to little or no family support.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The study has revealed that women who are suffering from VVF in Akwa Ibom State are stigmatized. The reason for the findings could be as a result of the offensive odour that comes from them. This can make them appear to be irritating to people. Even their close friends can feel uncomfortable staying close to them. The stigmatization can lead to abandonment of these women to fend for themselves even with their situation. This is in line with Khisa (2010), who stated that married survivors often are abandoned or forced to separate from their husbands. He further stated that in some cases, in-laws support the survivors and are sympathetic to their plight, on the other hand, the majority contribute to their ostracizing and at times advise their relatives to leave the woman with obstetric fistula and marry another wife. Left without any social or material support, the survivors' situation deteriorates as they often lack basic necessities such as food, shelter, water, soap among others. The finding of this study is similar to that of Emma-Echiegu, *et al.*, (2014) who reported that women living with VVF are stigmatized. The researcher further stated that many of them are avoided, made jest of, laughed at, or mocked. Some stated that they can only relate with their relatives, while others do not want to have anything to do with them. They would not even be allowed to share food no

matter how neatly they appear to dress as people will not collect their food they share.

On the rehabilitation of VVF survivors who have undergone successful surgery, the findings of the study indicated that what is commonly done is helping them to learn trade and providing counselling services. The family life Centre at Mbribit Itam makes provision for these women to learn tailoring and hair dressing in their facility. Trainers are employed by the management of the facility to train these women. Many of them have gone far with the training while others are just starting. These ones appear happy, especially now that they are free from the sickness. Interaction with them indicated that before their surgery, they were not happy people because they were sidelined and rejected by many people. However, they now see life differently after the surgery, since they are trying to mix and interact with others in the process of their training. They find it easier to interact with their colleagues who have also been successfully repaired. With time, they extended their interaction and association to others who visit the centre. The finding of the study is similar to that of Khisa (2010) who identified skill training as one of the major rehabilitation strategies adopted to reintegrate women who have successfully undergone VVF repair.

On the effect of counselling services on the rehabilitation of women who have successfully been repaired of VVF, the study indicated that the family life centre provides both group and individual counselling services to these women. Many of them have reported how beneficial the counselling services have been to them in trying to associate with others. The reason for the findings could be that many of these women might still be looking down on themselves and considering that they have very little or low self-worth compared to others. They might also consider all men as being evil, since their husbands or boyfriends were responsible for the pregnancy that led to their situations. Counselling services provided by the centre might have helped these ones to see life differently and forgive those that hurt them while they were suffering from the sickness. The finding of this study is similar to that of Khisa (2010) who also reported counselling as one of the major factors that help in reintegrating women who have successfully completed VVF repair.

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings of this study, it was concluded that women suffering from VVF are stigmatized and that the common reintegration strategies adopted after their repairs were skill training, counselling and family support.

RECOMMENDATIONS

1. The government should expand surgical facilities to make it easy for women suffering from VVF to access treatment, since this can ease the reintegration process.
2. Reintegration program designers should bear in mind that all girls and women with fistula are not the same, as such, reintegration strategies need to address the different situations in which these women may find themselves.
3. There should be couple counselling services before and after surgery to help the survivors' husband to cooperate and support the reintegration process.

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